

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON COMPANY PERFORMANCE IN MSME IN THE PROCESSING INDUSTRY

Moh. Mukhsin¹, Najmudin², Maulana M. Khadafi³

Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa Serang – Banten

Abstract

This study aimed to comprehensively examine the connections between eco-design, eco-manufacturing, and eco-purchasing practices to enhance business performance. The sample consisted of 100 respondents from MSME players in the processing industry in Serang City, Banten Province, Indonesia, selected by proportionate random sampling. Furthermore, the primary approach employed was SmartPLS, and the data were obtained by delivering questionnaires to the participants. The results showed that eco-design, green manufacturing and green purchasing had a positive and significant relationship with company performance. Therefore, using green supply chain management techniques is crucial for raising business performance.

Keywords: Eco Design, Green Manufacturing, Green Purchasing, and Company Performance.

1. Introduction

The rapid market and technological development in the information age have resulted in heightened competition within the commercial sector. Companies of varying sizes, including large, medium-sized, and small-scale businesses, all encounter escalating competition. Furthermore, consumer expectations for superior goods and market demand are subject to fluctuations. This becomes challenging for business entities to produce high-quality goods given the prevailing business competition and market demand. Numerous factors, such as processes, human resources, and interrelated systems, significantly influence the quality of a product. Business entities committed to environmentally friendly production also share concerns in this regard. One of the measures adopted to offer the finest products while prioritizing environmental sustainability is the implementation of an environmentally friendly supply chain, commonly known as green supply chain management.

A supply chain management technique related to environmental concerns is known as "green supply chain management." The presence of green supply chain management is anticipated to reduce or eliminate waste, including solid waste, hazardous chemicals, emissions, and energy. A strategy used to accomplish profitability and market share targets while lowering the risk of adverse impact on the environment is green supply chain management (Puryono & Kurniawan, 2017). To minimize waste and environmental impacts resulting from the activities of a business or industry, the concept was established (Hasan et al., 2016). According to (Khan & Qianli, 2017), three factors, namely eco-design, green manufacturing, and green purchasing are used to gauge the effectiveness of green supply chain management strategies. The techniques have an impact on how well manufacturing organizations perform. The advantages of these practices in a business benefit in terms of cost savings, such as lowering energy and water use, improving public perception, as well as environmental responsibility (Chin et al., 2015). Green supply chain

management techniques encompass initiatives that unite suppliers, customers, and the environmental challenges encountered by businesses, and can be used by MSME and major corporations.

In the past five years, MSME's share of the national gross domestic product increased from 57.84% to 60.34%. In the same time frame, employment increased from 96.99% to 97.22%. The sector has very limited access to the global industrial supply chain, despite rising indices of its contribution to GDP formation and labor absorption. Additionally, the MSME sector comprises only 0.8% of the global supply chain. Within the ASEAN region, countries such as Brunei, Laos, Myanmar, and Cambodia surpass Indonesia in their contributions to the global supply chains. The sector's contribution of 2.7% to the global stands out as the highest, and the presence of a substantial number indicates the existence of intense competition. MSME companies must also prioritize and address the aspect of environmental unpredictability to formulate a robust strategy.

MSME represents a vital sector in the ongoing development of industries and enterprises, and their contribution to the national economy is substantial. Moreover, the methods employed have a positive impact on maintaining environmental equilibrium. To thrive in the market, each MSME enhances productivity, improves service efficiency, and fosters swift and seamless innovation creation (Ambarwati et al., 2019). Enterprises must also manufacture high-quality goods and implement innovations such as applying green principles to products. Weak legislation, lax enforcement of the law, and a lack of awareness are the main barriers to the application of the concept, particularly for MSME sectors or firms (Amaranti et al., 2017). The use of the "green" idea is based on rising environmental consciousness.

This study focused on MSME participants in Serang City's processing sector in Indonesia. Therefore, the processing industry must take some steps to combat and lessen the effects of environmental pollution. The adoption of green supply chain management strategies is important for organizations to effectively address the management of waste generated during industrial product processing. To actively contribute to sustainable growth, this strategy must be embraced by all sectors of business (Heriyanto & Noviardy, 2019). According to (Khan & Qianli, 2017), green supply chain management directly influences the level of environmental responsibility demonstrated by a company. Furthermore, the implementation of the techniques significantly impacts the manufacturing processes of both companies and businesses, particularly in terms of environmental considerations. These techniques play a crucial role in facilitating ongoing performance improvement.

2. Theoretical Studies

The study conducted by (Al-Ghdabi et al., 2019) shows that green supply chain management techniques have a statistically significant impact on the company's reputation, and the direct influence is evident. In 2018, Rohdayatin, Sugito, and Handayani conducted a study titled "Green Supply Chain: Study of Its Relationship with Environmental Performance and Financial Performance" to explore the interconnection among environmentally friendly supply chain management, financial performance, and environmental performance. It focuses on the study population consisting of all eateries in Malang City, selected through proportionate random sampling using PLS method. The result shows the impact of green supply chain management on financial success, highlighting the significance of effective governance in raising performance. Furthermore, it demonstrates the influence of environmentally friendly supply chain management on performance, emphasizing the importance of green supply chain management governance in

enhancing environmental performance. Additionally, (Mafini & Muposhi, 2017) conducted a study titled "The Impact of Green Supply Chain Management in Small to Medium Enterprises: Cross-Sectional Evidence" to ascertain the connection between environmental cooperation, green supply chain management techniques, and SME financial success. This study is quantitative and included 312 MSME in the Gauteng province of South Africa. Confirmatory factor analysis was used to verify the measuring scale's psychometric qualities, while structural equation modelling verified the presented hypothesis. The findings demonstrated that MSME achieved financial success due to environmental cooperation through the adoption of green supply chain management strategies. A study titled "The Relationship Between Green Supply Chain Management and Performance: A Meta-Analysis of Empirical Evidence in Asian Emerging Economics" was conducted by (Geng et al., 2017). The primary aim was to understand the connection between supply chain management and corporate success in the manufacturing sector of Asian Emerging Economies (AEE). The analysis reported 50 studies published between 1996 and 2015 that surveyed 11,127 industrial enterprises in the EEA. The findings demonstrated that using green supply chain management techniques improved economic, environmental, operational, and social performance. A study titled "Impact of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on Firm's Performance: an Empirical Study from The Perspective of Pakistan" was performed by (Khan & Qianli, 2017). In the context of Pakistani manufacturing enterprises, it investigated the effects of five green supply chain practices determinants on organizational performance. A total of five independent variables, namely green manufacturing, green purchasing, green information systems, customer collaboration, and eco-design, were used to gauge the effectiveness of the strategies. Meanwhile, concurrent regression analysis and factor exploration were used in this investigation. The findings demonstrated that eco-design, green information systems, green manufacturing, and customer collaboration significantly impact organizational performance. Other results also supported the notion that green purchasing is detrimental to organizational success. A study titled "Application of Green Supply Chain Management to Improve Company Financial Performance" was conducted in 2016 by (Puryono et al., 2017), and Jie, while "Green Supply Chain Management, Environmental Collaboration and Sustainability Performance" was performed by (Chin et al., 2015). To analyze the data, this study employed SEM and focused on a population of 37,694 enterprises representing Malaysia's media and manufacturing industries. The results showed a robust correlation between sustainable performance and green supply chain management. In 2015, Choi and Hwang conducted a study titled "The Impact of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on Firm Performance: The Role of Collaborative Capability." This study investigated survey data collected from 230 South Korean manufacturers to examine the influence of collaborative capabilities on mitigating the impact of green supply chain management techniques on business performance. The findings suggested that the implementation can enhance the financial and environmental performance of a company. Furthermore, active collaboration with various partners strengthens the link between green supply chain management techniques and financial performance.

2.1 Supply Chain Management

According to (佐野輝樹, 2015), a supply chain is a group of businesses that collaborate to develop products and move materials, information, and cash from suppliers to consumers. Environmentally responsible supply chain management protects the natural world and the environment by considering the effects of all operations and products. (Azizah & Pramandari, 2018) asserted that

several key players, including suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, retailers, and customers, have a stake in the movement of commodities. Supply chain management is a technique, instrument, or strategy for managing supplies. Furthermore, the production and distribution of a good or service are carried out through a series of organizations, according to (Mukhsin et al., 2022). These organizations perform various tasks and activities. In supply chain management, the material context also includes completed goods, auxiliary materials, components, semi-finished goods, and various pieces of equipment (Azizah & Pramandari, 2018). The management of continuous improvement is one of the core components. Meanwhile, a measuring system that supports overall supply chain performance is supported by effective performance (Mustaniroh et al., 2019).

According to (Brilliana et al., 2020), creating new products, acquiring raw materials, scheduling manufacturing and inventory, carrying out production, shipping or distributing items, and accepting returns are the major operations of supply chain management. The concept consists of three primary parts, namely upstream, internal, and downstream supply chain (Azizah & Pramandari, 2018).

Supply chain management techniques, according to (Chin et al., 2015), comprise several actions that businesses utilize successfully to connect supply and demand. Implementing the procedures can result in advantages such as decreased inventory levels, shortened production lead times, enhanced flexibility, cost savings, and precise resource planning. The fundamental tenets are consistent with (Heriyanto & Noviardy, 2019), and comprised of five elements, namely the concepts of integration, networking, end-to-end, and dependency. (Wulandari et al., 2017) demonstrated that supply chain management improves business performance. The concept is the coordination of business function strategies in an organization to fuse supply and demand management.

2.2 Green Supply Chain Management

According to (Al-Ghdabi et al., 2019), green supply chain management is a set of procedures that includes a variety of tasks such as idea generation and development, environmentally friendly product design, purchasing, shipping, manufacturing, and waste management. (Rakhmawati et al., 2019) stated that "green supply chain management" instructs all factors and components of the supply chain to minimize or mitigate harmful effects on the environment. According to (Chin et al., 2015), the implementation is well-positioned to enhance sustainability performance in terms of the economy, environment, and society. Employing the concept can give businesses appealing competitive benefits, and offers financial advantages. (Choi & Hwang, 2015) stated that the concept is the activity of enhancing environmental performance throughout the supply chain, including product design.

Green supply chain management techniques have been implemented to improve the company's financial and environmental performance. The concept emerges to incorporate the concept of environmental protection, encompassing procurement procedures, manufacturing processes utilizing clean technology, distribution of finished products to consumers, and end-of-product-life recycling (Djunaidi et al., 2018). Additionally, attempts to reduce a company's negative effects on the environment concerning climate change, pollution, and non-renewable resources are referred to as "green supply chain management" (Heriyanto & Noviardy, 2019).

2.2.1 Eco-Design

By incorporating environmental factors into the life cycle of a product, from the procurement of raw materials to final disposal, eco-design develops sustainable products (Choi & Hwang, 2015). On the part of product or process design, it is regarded as the primary instrument for preventing pollution in most product characteristics. The following list includes some eco-design tactics, namely using less energy and water during production, less packaging during distribution, and using recyclable and renewable materials during the procurement stage. Eco-design also refers to ecological, sustainable, environmental, and environmentally conscious design, focusing on creating eco-friendly products by minimizing waste and maximizing material utilization (Chuang & Yang, 2014). Furthermore, it reduces greenhouse gas emissions at the use stage. The concept also reduces the harmful environmental effects of products for their entire cycle. The ultimate goal is to increase the competitive advantage of green products in addition to eliminating negative environmental effects. (Al-Ghdabi et al., 2019) stated that eco-design is viewed as one step in the development of a product to enhance environmental friendliness (Inkiriwang, 2018). According to (Khan & Qianli, 2017), it helps a company's environmental sustainability and environmental performance to create a competitive advantage and enhance financial performance.

2.2.2 Green Manufacturing

To protect the environment, green manufacturing aims to eliminate hazardous waste during the production process (Khan & Qianli, 2017). Sustainable manufacturing, which may be attained by implementing the green concept, is strongly related to this variable (Amaranti et al., 2017). According to (Al-Ghdabi et al., 2019), it is a system that integrates concerns about product and process design with corporate planning, as well as identifying, measuring, and controlling environmental waste streams to reduce environmental impact. Green manufacturing also prioritizes the development of systems that mitigate detrimental environmental impacts through the modification of raw material management, energy utilization, and product manufacturing processes. According to (Subramanian & Gunasekaran, 2015), the concept is a cutting-edge method that addresses issues including waste reduction, pollution prevention, energy conservation, and health and safety. (Gandhi et al., 2018) stated that the use can boost market share, competitive advantage, and brand image. Meanwhile, numerous opportunities are presented by green manufacturing for businesses and the environment. This serves as a standard for groups or businesses aiming to balance performance in the social, environmental, and economic spheres (Agyabeng-Mensah et al., 2020). Environmentally conscious design, reducing the usage of harmful substances, and pollution avoidance are all part of the concept.

2.2.3 Green Purchasing

Green buying is the practice of making environmentally conscious purchases. According to (Khan & Qianli, 2017), it is the practice of prioritizing ecologically friendly concepts while making product choices. In terms of the concept, there are seven factors to consider, namely the kind of product, shape, brand, sales, quality, when to buy it, and how to pay. By incorporating environmental concerns into product specifications and supplier selection, green purchasing improves environmental performance ((Namagembe et al., 2018). Furthermore, it is defined as consumers' intention and subsequent action to purchase ecologically friendly goods, reflecting their readiness to prioritize environmentally sustainable options.

2.2.4 Company Performance

(Choi & Hwang, 2015) asserted that a company's performance is the end outcome of its actions over a specific period and is influenced by its operational activities and resources. Improved firm performance is one of the effects of green supply chain management on business performance. Green supply chain management directly affects company performance and can assist businesses in enhancing their capacity. The following describes the evaluation of the company performance based on environmental and financial factors:

1. Environmental Performance

According to (Choi & Hwang, 2015), environmental performance is the ecological outcome of a company's dedication to protecting and enhancing the environment. This assessment focuses on the actions that influence the environment, such as cutting back on waste, solid waste, and environmentally hazardous gases. Environmental improvement and the adoption of green supply chain management strategies are positively correlated (Choi & Hwang, 2015). The advancement of the objectives will be achieved through the active engagement of environmentally conscious suppliers. Additionally, the implementation of green supply chain management strategies enables businesses to enhance their management capabilities to drive performance improvements.

2. Financial Performance

Revenue can be used to improve the financial performance of a company. Companies that perform well in terms of the environment advance and succeed financially (Choi & Hwang, 2015). Meanwhile, those that prioritize the environmental impact of their operations are likely to experience enhanced financial performance through cost savings in production and improved resource management. Green supply chain management practices specifically focus on waste disposal in alignment with environmental sustainability objectives. These waste reduction measures contribute to environmental preservation and lead to reduced expenses, bolstering financial stability.

2.1 Relationships Between Variables

2.1.1 Eco-design affects company performance

According to (Choi & Hwang, 2015), "eco-design" is a term that includes "green design," "design for the environment," "sustainable design," and other terms. The findings of (Green et al., 2012) demonstrated a correlation between increasing environmental and financial work and the adoption of green supply chain management. (Choi & Hwang, 2015) stated that eco-design is acknowledged as a cutting-edge tool to improve performance rather than the environment. The innovations can increase a company's sales growth in addition to enhancing its reputation or image (Choi & Hwang, 2015). According to (Choi & Hwang, 2015), eco-design has several benefits indirectly related to lower production costs. The combination of eco-design and green supply chain management helps businesses improve their environmental management skills and results in improved performance. The following hypothesis is developed since eco-design has an impact on business performance based on earlier study:

H1: There is an influence of eco-design on company performance

2.1.2 Green manufacturing affects company performance

Employing optimal resources is a fundamental necessity for green production. The concept of green manufacturing encompasses techniques that prioritize the environment and minimizes waste

while mitigating air, water, and soil pollution through effective product and process design. By adopting these practices, companies can ensure that their industrial processes align with environmental preservation goals (Amaranti et al., 2017). Furthermore, green manufacturing directs the production process by producing high-quality goods at the most affordable price (Khan & Qianli, 2017). Companies that use the technology can cut expenses and waste while implementing a green process. According to (Subramanian & Gunasekaran, 2015), the use of the concept in the production processes of the automobile sector has greatly expanded. (Prajogo & Olhager, 2012) stated that green manufacturing works to decrease environmental waste and boost productivity. The practice of green supply chain management places a strong emphasis on the use of the concept to lessen the negative consequences of production operations and produce less waste. Efficient waste management undoubtedly contributes to environmental protection, while positively impacting the economy and production efficiency. It serves as a crucial step towards environmental preservation. Based on this rationale, the performance of a company improves proportionately with the effective utilization of green manufacturing practices. This conclusion is supported by previous findings, which have consistently demonstrated the influence of the concept on business performance. Considering these findings, the following hypothesis has been formulated:

H2: There is an influence of green manufacturing on company performance

2.1.3 Green purchasing affects company performance

Green supply chain management can be a strategy to conserve resources because green purchasing contributes to waste reduction through recycling (Khan & Qianli, 2017). By engaging in recycling activities, the concept can reduce waste, which can affect cost economics and environmental pollution control. These actions have the impact of improving the company's market reputation and environmental performance. According to (Khan & Qianli, 2017), green purchasing creates a competitive advantage, enhances business performance, and safeguards natural resources. The performance of an organization is directly and favorably impacted by the concept. The implementation of the practices is designed to protect the environment from hazardous and harmful substances, and it exerts a significant impact on the overall operation of a business. (Chuang & Yang, 2014) categorized green purchasing into five primary categories, namely supply chain management, ecology, environmental authentication, design operations management, and external environmental management. These categories inherently exert an immediate influence on the performance of a company. The utilization of more effective implementation increases the performance of the company. This hypothesis is formulated based on earlier findings that establish the impact of purchasing on business performance.

H3: There is an effect of green purchasing on company performance

2.2 Frame of Mind

The implementation of green supply chain management, as measured by eco-design (X1), green manufacturing (X2), and green purchasing (X3) as exogenous factors, and firm performance (Y) as endogenous variables, are employed in this study. According to the findings, the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables can be seen in the mental image as follows:

Figure 1. Study Model Path Diagram
Source: Processed Primary Data, 2026

3. Study Methods

This study employs an explanatory quantitative technique to demonstrate hypotheses using quantifiable data and yields conclusions. According to (Mukhsin, 2023), the goal of quantitative study is to establish correlations between the variables, test hypotheses, and search for generalizations with predictive significance.

3.1 Study Variables

Variables are measured and evaluated, such as symbols, events, behaviors, treatments, and traits (Rahi, 2017). Studies are conducted based on exogenous and endogenous variables. Exogenous variables have an impact on positive and negative effects (Articles, 2021). The utilization of green supply chain management as measured by eco-design (X1), green manufacturing (X2), and green purchasing (X3) constitutes the exogenous factors. Furthermore, endogenous variables are the focus of attention and debate in academic studies. Performance of the companies was the endogenous variable employed in this study.

Each construct was operationalized using multiple reflective indicators adapted from prior validated studies to ensure content validity and construct reliability (Chin et al., 2015; Khan & Qianli, 2017). Eco-design was measured through indicators related to environmentally friendly product design, efficient use of resources, and product lifecycle considerations (Choi & Hwang, 2015). Green manufacturing included indicators such as waste reduction, energy efficiency, and environmentally responsible production processes (Subramanian & Gunasekaran, 2015). Green

purchasing was measured through supplier environmental evaluation, selection of eco-friendly materials, and sustainability-oriented procurement practices (Namagembe et al., 2018). Company performance was assessed using both financial and environmental performance indicators, reflecting a multidimensional evaluation of organizational outcomes (Chin et al., 2015; Geng et al., 2017). All indicators were measured using a Likert scale to capture respondents' perceptions consistently and to support the application of PLS-SEM analysis.

3.2 Population and Sample

According to (Mukhsin et al., 2022), population encompasses the broad scope of the entire subject of study, which can include individuals, social groups, events, or other specifically defined subjects sharing common qualities, characteristics, or attributes. It refers to the generalization domain of the study subject. (Mukhsin et al., 2022) stated that samples are a representation of the size and features of a population or subgroup. Conclusions extrapolated to the entire population can be reached by studying samples, which are the subset of the selected individuals. Due to constraints such as limited resources and time, it is common to utilize samples to investigate the entire population.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Results

To evaluate the validity and reliability of models developed with convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability, measurement model testing is used. The goal of convergent validity is to assess the degree to which the indicators of variable measurement outcomes and the theoretical ideas are consistent. The test can be assessed using outer loadings, composite reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). A table of loading factors known as outer loadings are used to display the strength of the association between indicators and latent variables. Furthermore, the loading factor is acceptable when the number is greater than 0.60. Figure 2 displays the results of the route chart analysis, providing a clearer representation of the outer loading of indicator blocks used to evaluate constructions.

Figure 2. First Estimate Result Path Diagram
Source: Processed Primary Data, 2026

Figure 2 demonstrates that some indicators' loading factors are invalid since they have coefficients below 0.70. These indicators must be removed, namely Eco_des1 (0.246), Eco_des4 (0.049), Green_man3 (0.673), Green_pur3 (0.017), Com_per1 (0.155), Com_per3 (0.692), and Com_per6 (0.609). Subsequently, re-estimating or re-estimation can occur after removing the indicators. Re-estimation is intended to reevaluate the reliability of the loading factor to examine the measurement model. The model path diagram in Figure 3 shows the re-estimation results as follows:

Figure 3. Re-estimation Results Path Chart
Source: Processed Primary Data, 2026

Figure 3 illustrates how the re-estimation of each indicator, employed for evaluating the construct, influences the loading factor. The findings demonstrate that all indicators have strong validity because their loading factors are greater than 0.70. The AVE value is used to determine convergent validity as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Average Variance Extracted (AVE).

Construct	AVE
Company Performance	0.654
Eco Design	0.698
Green Manufacturing	0.697
Green Purchasing	0.661

Source: Results of Primary Data Analysis, 2026

Additionally, a reliability test is used to check the consistency of signs in one latent variable. Cronbach's alpha and the composite reliability value can be used to gauge the reliability of testing. Cronbach's alpha should be higher than 0.6 and the composite reliability value must be higher than 0.70 for a construct to be deemed reliable.

Table 2. Results of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Company Performance	0.817	0.881
Eco Design	0.782	0.873
Green Manufacturing	0.781	0.873
Green Purchasing	0.742	0.853

Source: Results of Primary Data Analysis, 2026

The inner model utilizes substantive theory to define the relationships between latent variables. The R-square value indicates the degree of influence of the endogenous variable on the exogenous. A higher R-square score indicates a stronger relationship, and the calculated values are 0.67 (strong), 0.33 (moderate), and 0.19 (weak).

Table 3. R-square value

Construct	R-square
Company Performance	0.817
Eco Design	0.782
Green Manufacturing	0.781
Green Purchasing	0.742

Source: Results of Primary Data Analysis, 2026

The calculation results of R-square for each endogenous latent variable in Table 3 indicate that the company performance variable possesses a strong value of 0.817. This demonstrates that the Eco Design variable influences the company performance by 0.817 or 81.7%, and the remaining 18.3% is influenced by other factors. Furthermore, the R-square value of 0.817 indicates a substantial explanatory power of the model, suggesting that the combined effects of eco-design, green manufacturing, and green purchasing provide a strong prediction of company performance. This highlights the robustness of the structural model in explaining performance variations among MSMEs. Moreover, this high explanatory power confirms that the selected GSCM dimensions are not only statistically significant but also practically relevant in influencing organizational

outcomes, thereby strengthening the predictive capability and empirical validity of the model. Based on these test findings, the measurement model exhibits favorable validity and reliability, allowing for further hypothesis testing. This study employs three criteria, namely the original sample, t-statistic, and p-value, which must be satisfied to test the hypothesis. The original sample value is used to ascertain the direction of the hypothesis testing, a positive and negative original sample value signifies a positive and negative direction. Subsequently, t-statistics are employed to determine the significance, and the direction of the hypothesis needs to be established before using t-statistics. In this study, the t-table value and the t-statistic value generated by the PLS output are compared.

The acceptance criteria at a 5% significance level dictate that the hypothesis is accepted or rejected when the t-count is greater or less than the t-table value of 1.96. Additionally, the p-value serves as a final criterion to determine the significance of the result. To accept a hypothesis, a p-value of 0.05 or lower is required. All three requirements must be met for a hypothesis to be accepted, and when any of these are not satisfied, it is rejected. Considering the representation of the outcomes of the PLS Version 3 analysis in Table 4, further conclusions can be drawn.

Table 4. Summary of Hypothesis Test Results

Construct	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Value	Description
Eco Design→Company Performance	0.230	3.197	0.001	Significant: H ₁ Accepted
Green Manufacturing→Company Performance	0.382	2.956	0.003	Significant: H ₂ Accepted
Green Purchasing→Company Performance	0.380	2.966	0.003	Significant: H ₃ Accepted

Source: Results of Primary Data Analysis, 2026

Table 4 shows that the original sample value for the influence of eco-design on company performance is 0.230. Since the t-statistic value of 3.197 is higher than the t-table value (significance level 5%=1.96) and the p-value is less than 0.05, hypothesis 1 is supported. Based on the analysis of Table 4, implementing eco-design in MSME companies within the processing industry in Serang City, Banten Province, Indonesia lead to an improvement in Company Performance. Therefore, accepting the first hypothesis proposed in this investigation is justified. The second hypothesis states that green manufacturing influences performance. According to Table 4, the relationship between green manufacturing and company performance exhibits an original sample value of 0.382, a t-statistic value exceeding the t-table value of 2.956 (at a 5% significance level of 1.96), and a P-value of 0.003, lower than 0.05. The utilization of green manufacturing significantly impacts the performance of MSME operators in the processing industry of Serang City, Banten Province, Indonesia. Consequently, the second hypothesis of the study has been confirmed.

The third theory contends that MSME participants have lower company performance as a result of green purchasing. According to Table 4, the relationship has an original sample value of 0.380, a t-statistic value more than the t-table of 2.966 (significance level 5% = 1.96), and a p-value less than 0.05 of 0.003 with a t-statistic value of 2.966. The use of green purchasing has a big impact on the performance of MSME operators in Serang City's processing industry in Banten Province, Indonesia, hence the third hypothesis has been verified.

4.2 Discussion

4.2.1 The Effect of Eco-Design on Company Performance

According to the descriptive analysis, eco-design positively impacts business performance. The findings are consistent with study conducted by Green supply chain management practices, where the environment and the financial sectors have a favorable impact on the implementation of the concept. In addition, eco-design has been acknowledged as a cutting-edge instrument to enhance business performance (Choi & Hwang, 2015). The implementation and the use of green supply chain management assist businesses build their environmental management capabilities and improve performance. Therefore, eco-design has an impact on business performance based on the findings of the previous study.

However, the relatively lower coefficient value compared to other GSCM dimensions indicates that eco-design may generate performance improvements in a more gradual and long-term manner. This is because eco-design primarily focuses on product development and lifecycle efficiency, which require time to translate into measurable financial outcomes (Manoj Kumar et al., 2025). From a strategic perspective, eco-design can be viewed as a capability-building mechanism that strengthens innovation and sustainability orientation. Furthermore, its impact may be mediated by factors such as organizational learning and environmental awareness, which enhance the firm's ability to convert design initiatives into performance gains (Matta et al., 2019)

4.2.2 The Effect of Green Manufacturing on Company Performance

According to the questionnaire responses from MSME owners of batik businesses, green manufacturing improves performance, as evident by the company's rising market share. The findings are consistent with (Subramanian & Gunasekaran, 2015), which demonstrated a considerable increase in green manufacturing among businesses in the automotive sector. Green manufacturing reduces waste to the environment and boosts production efficiency (Prajogo & Olhager, 2012). The practice of green supply chain management places a strong emphasis on the use of the variable to lessen the negative consequences of production operations and produce less waste. Furthermore, waste can undoubtedly improve environmental protection, and enhances economy, production efficiency, and preservation.

The stronger effect of green manufacturing on company performance suggests that operational improvements provide more immediate and tangible benefits for MSMEs. By directly reducing waste, energy consumption, and production costs, green manufacturing contributes to both efficiency gains and cost savings, which are critical for small and medium enterprises. This finding reinforces the importance of integrating environmental considerations into core production processes. Additionally, the effectiveness of green manufacturing practices may be influenced by external factors such as regulatory pressure and technological capability, which can moderate the extent to which these practices translate into performance outcomes (Zhong & Um, 2025).

4.2.3 The Effect of Green Purchasing on Company Performance

According to descriptive data from the survey responses, green purchasing has a favorable impact on performance, as evident in business earnings. The findings are consistent with (Khan & Qianli,

2017), where recycling operations can minimize trash, affecting cost economics and environmental pollution control. The performance of an organization is directly and favorably impacted by green purchasing. The implementation is intended to safeguard the environment from dangerous and harmful substances as well as has a substantial effect on the operation of the business. The performance of the company increases when green purchasing is used more effectively. Therefore, green purchasing is required to maximize the impact on business performance.

The relatively strong influence of green purchasing highlights the strategic role of supplier selection and procurement practices in shaping organizational performance. By collaborating with environmentally responsible suppliers and prioritizing eco-friendly materials, firms can improve supply chain efficiency while enhancing their environmental reputation. This not only reduces operational risks but also strengthens market competitiveness. Moreover, the impact of green purchasing may be mediated by supply chain integration and collaboration, as well as moderated by market demand for sustainable products, which determines the extent to which these practices generate economic returns (Park et al., 2022).

5. Conclusion

The following conclusions can be drawn based on the findings on eco-design, green manufacturing, green purchasing, and corporate performance among MSME participants in the processing industry of Serang City, Banten Province, Indonesia. Firstly, the impact of eco-design on company performance is evident. This highlights the importance of implementing effective eco-design governance in the processing sector to enhance business performance. Secondly, green manufacturing significantly influences corporate performance. The utilization of eco-design plays a crucial role in determining the degree of company performance. This emphasizes the significance of green manufacturing governance in the processing sector for improving the performance of MSME operators in Serang City, Banten Province, Indonesia. The concern of the processing sector with the environment is directly proportional to green manufacturing. Finally, green purchasing affects business performance. This underscores the significance of implementing effective green purchasing governance in the processing sector to enhance business performance. The level of performance increases with the effective implementation of green purchasing.

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